

INSTRUMENTS FOR IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATIONAL SERVICES IN THE NATIONAL INNOVATION SYSTEM

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Annotation: This article highlights the implementation of the goals set in concept for the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030. At the same time, the model was analyzed cooperation between universities and subjects of the national innovation system.

Keywords: national economy, national innovation system, the science, technopark, integration, endowment fund, innovative enterprises.

National innovation systems (NIS) in most cases are formed during periods when an exchange of technological structures occurs. During the initial period of formation of the national innovation system, there will be no integral system of connections between subjects of investment activity. The state occupies a special place in establishing these connections and developing a general investment strategy. Then, as in most industrialized countries, businesses in this area will take the lead. But it is unknown which model will be effective for a particular system. To explain national differences in the level of technological development, S.Metcalfé proposed using the concept of the Massachusetts Institute of Technology.

S.Metcalfé argued that the National Innovation System is a

“collection of various institutions that influence innovation processes, provide the basis for government policy formation and implementation, and contribute jointly or separately to the creation and diffusion of new technologies.” He believes that it is a system interconnected institutions needed to create, maintain and transfer the tools, skills and knowledge that shape the development of new technologies.¹

B.Lundvall defines that “a system of innovation consists of elements and relationships that interact in the generation, dissemination and use of knowledge that is new and has high economic efficiency, and that such a system includes elements and relationships that are within the national state or begin at this territory”².

“The National Innovation System is a set of interconnected organizations engaged in the production and commercialization of new scientific knowledge and technologies within national borders. Meanwhile, the National Innovation System is a set of legal, financial and social institutions that ensure the implementation of innovative investment processes that have strong national roots, traditions, political and cultural identity”³.

The national innovation system is a complex of interconnected structures that serve for the creation, implementation and commercialization of scientific knowledge and technologies within the national territory⁴.

The national innovation system includes two structural divisions: research and production and institutional. The institutional environment ensures the functioning and innovation policy of the state in the field of science and

¹ Metcalfe S. Steinman P. (ed.) The economic Foundations of Technology Policy: Equilibrium and Evolutionary Perspectives // Handbook of the Economics of Innovation and Technical Change. – London. Blackwell. 1995. P. 462-463

² Lundvall BA National Systems of Innovation. – London: Pinter.1992. P.2.

³ Ivanova N.I. National innovation systems. – M.: Science. 2002.- p.7.

⁴ Zhuraev T.T. Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi okuv qullanma. – T.: Fan va technology, 2017.-B.54

technology.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 8, 2019 PD-5847 “On approval of the Concept for the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030” adopted the concept for the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030.⁵ The concept is aimed at improving the higher education system, training competitive personnel, effective organization of scientific and innovative activities based on ensuring strong integration of science, education and production, based on the needs of the social sphere and economic sectors.

A feature of this strategy is the development of public-private partnerships in the field of higher education, ensuring the level of enrollment in higher education above 50% based on the organization of activities of state and non-state higher education institutions, including branches of prestigious foreign higher education institutions, creating a competitive environment in the field of higher education . The inclusion of the National University of Uzbekistan and Samarkand State University in the list of 500 best universities will be achieved.

The higher education system is an important pillar that increases the national wealth and competitiveness of the country. According to the experience of developed countries, to ensure sustainable economic growth, 40-50% of the population must have higher education, and in the knowledge economy the share of highly educated people reaches 60%. In the Republic of Uzbekistan: “In recent years, the number of our universities has increased 2.5 times to 198, the enrollment rate has increased from 9% to 38%. We aim to increase these numbers even further. But the question of what will happen to the quality of education should make us all think. First of all, each university

⁵ Uzbekistan Republic Presidential 2019 October 8th “Uzbekistan Republicsi Oliy talim tizimini 2030 yilgacha rivozhlantirish conceptsini tasdiqlash tugrisida”gi PF-5847 – son farmoni.

should try to do this on its own, then the result will come.⁶

The development of the higher education system can be divided into two periods. The first period is 2012–2016. During this period, indicators of the development of higher education system services are declining.

During this period, it can be observed that the number of students admitted to the higher education system on the basis of budget and contract decreased and, accordingly, the share of higher education system services in gross services decreased from 4.5% in 2010 to 4.0% in 2016. The second period, 2017-2021, is a period of growth in the services of the higher education system during the period of action of the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In our opinion, given the acceleration of the formation of an innovative economy in the republic, it is advisable to reform it by developing a system of measures in the following areas in order to increase the volume of services of the higher education system.

First of all, it is necessary to further increase the level of population coverage with higher education in the republic. Considering that state educational institutions cannot do this on their own, it is necessary to further improve the mechanism for creating non-state higher educational institutions in the republic. A problematic issue for the republic is providing opportunities for higher education for a wider range of the population, as well as increasing the volume of training of personnel who play a key role in the formation and development of an innovative economy.

the entry of qualified personnel into the labor market reduces the influx and generally temporarily delays the load on the labor market;

⁶ Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Uzbekistan Republic President Shavkat Mirziyoyevning Oliy Majlisga Murozhaatnomasi. T.// Xalk s'zi, 2022, December 21.

secondly, from the experience of developed countries in improving the system of evening education or distance education for various segments of the population, including the elderly and people with limited access to education through full-time education programs, women with small children, working people, it is advisable for use;

thirdly, it is necessary to stimulate scientific research and innovation in higher education institutions. It is known that most of the scientific research and development in developed countries is carried out in universities. The implementation of this should ensure strengthening of ties between the state and the business sector, which are other participants in universities and innovation activities;

fourthly, strengthen the integration of the higher education system into the global education system. As a result of improving higher education, in contrast to the current situation, it is necessary to develop measures that, at a minimum, will encourage Central Asian countries to become exporters of higher education services.

An extensive innovation infrastructure has been formed in the Republic of Uzbekistan, which includes various stages of the creation and implementation of innovative ideas. However, this infrastructure is not used on demand due to poor communication between facilities, as well as lack of adequate collaboration and low motivation⁷.

In addition, in our country there is a gap between higher education, science and production, integration is not ensured, scientific research is carried out without taking into account the real needs of economic sectors, the lack of systematic training of highly qualified scientific and scientific-pedagogical personnel leads to a decrease in the scientific potential of universities.

⁷Eshboev A.Kh. Bozor munosabatlariga ўtish davrida talim tizimining milliy iqtisodiyotni rivozhlantirishga tasiri. I.f.n.ilm. gift. olish uchun yozilgan dis.abstract. – Tashkent, 2008.- B.8.

Today, many educational institutions offer mobile learning, and most people accept the offer. Mobile eLearning revenues will reach \$38 billion by the end of 2020. The US dollar is expected to exceed⁸.Therefore, close cooperation with government authorities allows educational and scientific organizations to expand opportunities for R&D development and attract additional funds. The model of interaction between higher education institutions and other elements of the national innovation system is presented in Figure 1.

As can be seen from Figure 1, the center of the model of interaction between universities and subjects of the national innovation system are organizations of science and education. They cooperate with the state, the population, the business sector and the innovation infrastructure. This cooperation is regulated and funded by the state. Financing of higher educational institutions is carried out through government programs and various funds of the national innovation system of scientific and educational organizations. The figure shows the reasons and levels of cooperation between scientific and educational organizations.

⁸André, Louie. “72 Essential LMS ELearning Statistics 2020 Market Share Data Analysis.” Finances Online, 27 Mar. 2020, financesonline.com/25-essential-learning-management-system-e-learning-statistics-analysis-of-trends-data-and-market-share/.

Figure 1. **Model of cooperation between universities and subjects of the national innovation system⁹**

The main task of government authorities is to support scientific research from the initial stage and create favorable conditions for the commercialization of innovations. The tools to facilitate such interaction are, first of all, establishing connections through government agencies, programs, subsidies, etc. The goal of interaction and integration of science, education and the business community is to create favorable conditions for the creation of knowledge and its generation. It is desirable for every university to have its own technology park, because here, with state, network and regional support, ideas turn into business.

⁹ Based on the author's research.

It is known that approximately 13% of technology parks are created according to the university model - as structural divisions of universities. Technology parks occupy a special place in the implementation of entrepreneurial activities in universities. Because there it is possible to produce products as a result of scientific and innovative activities. The potential of each university is not enough to organize a technology park. If the technology park is seen primarily as a priority for universities in the technical field, then at the same time, humanitarian and socio-economic universities will be able to take their place in the services market by providing consulting services.

Small innovative enterprises created on the basis of higher educational institutions play the role of a link between fundamental science and production. Universities must take into account the demand for innovative products on the market when forming a set of projects. Manufacturing companies use it in the process of creating an investment product, thereby turning knowledge into a product in demand on the market. In their activities to implement traditional and innovative functions, universities must create a favorable environment for the effective development of the country's enterprises.

In addition, the endowment fund and the culture of charity are poorly developed in Uzbekistan. World experience shows that most funds created to support scientific research and development are not tied to one university, but finance research conducted by scientists regardless of their place of work. The amount of funding directly determines the effectiveness and scale of research and development. There is a positive correlation between the size of a university's endowment funds and its place in the world rankings.

In international practice, such funds, as a rule, invest their funds in order to generate income, which is completely directed to the purposes envisaged by the founder, excluding the costs of managing the fund. To

increase the scale and efficiency of interaction between these subjects of the national innovation system, the following measures are necessary:

- Implementation of the concept of the “knowledge triangle”, based on three elements of the national innovation system, the triangle, higher educational institutions, cooperation between business and the state in three areas - innovation, scientific research and education.¹⁰;
- formation of cross-industry cooperation with industry, universities and venture partners;
- cooperation with enterprises through innovation infrastructure;
- Development of entrepreneurial culture in universities;
- Management of university network interactions.

We consider the use of digitalization tools to be a conceptually important solution to the proposed model. Digitalization ensures dramatic progress in technologies and products created by universities and provides them with the following additional opportunities:

- introduction of hybrid education;
- use of virtual laboratories, which are often expensive equipment;
- Internet marketing in the field of educational services.

The digitalization process leads to changes in requirements for professors and teachers, including the need for knowledge and proficiency in digital technologies. By 2025, the share of the digital economy in the world will be 23 trillion. reaches US dollars. Its share in global GDP will increase from the current 17.1% to 24.3%, the number of enterprises using cloud technologies will increase by 58%, artificial intelligence - by 86%, digital big data - by

¹⁰Hagen S. From Tech Transfer to knowledge exchange: European Universities in the Marketplace // WennerGren International Series. Vol. 84. The University in the Market. Portlan Press Ltd, 2008.

80%¹¹.

We believe that digitalization of universities can accelerate the development of small innovative enterprises through the use of the latest technologies in the educational process. Small innovative enterprises are an integral part of the innovation system within the university and, with the effective interaction of all tools for increasing the efficiency of the university's innovation activities, can act as a driver for the development of the university and act as the main core of innovation. .

Thus, to increase the efficiency of small innovative enterprises created in universities, it is necessary to create an innovative culture in universities, employee loyalty, transform education, change approaches to organizing research work, the system of motivation for scientists, as well as other scientific and educational organizations of universities, and it is necessary to use a wide range of tools aimed at the principles of cooperation with business.

List of used literature

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 8, 2019 No. PD-5847 “On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030.”
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 1, 2021 No. PD-5047 “On measures to further improve state policy in the field of science and innovative development.”
3. André, Louie “72 Essential LMS ELearning Statistics 2020 Market Share Data Analysis”. Finances Online, 27 March 2020, [finances online.com/25-essential-learning-management-system-e-learning-statistics-analysis-of-trends-data-and-market-share/](https://financesonline.com/25-essential-learning-management-system-e-learning-statistics-analysis-of-trends-data-and-market-share/).

¹¹Zufarova N.G. Oliy talimning brand capital - tashkilotning nomoddiy active sifatida. Magazine “Logistics va iktisod” 2022 yil No. 1 son.-B.158.

4. Metcalfe S. Steinman P. (ed.) The economic Foundations of Technology Policy: Equilibrium and Evolutionary Perspectives // Handbook of the Economics of Innovation and Technical Change. – London. Blackwell. 1995. P. 462-463
5. Lundvall B.A. National Systems of Innovation. – London: Pinter.1992. P.2.
6. Ivanova N.I. National innovation systems. – M.: Science. 2002.- p.7.
7. Juraev T.T. Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi – T.: Fan va technology, 2017.-B.54